

This is the accepted manuscript version of an article published in *TESOL Journal*.
The published version is available via DOI: 10.1002/tesj.305.

CITATION:

Mirhosseini, S. A. (2018). An invitation to the less-treaded path of autoethnography in TESOL research. *TESOL Journal*, 9(1), 76–92. DOI: 10.1002/tesj.305.

An invitation to the less-treaded path of autoethnography in TESOL research

Seyyed-Abdolhamid Mirhosseini

Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

Abstract

Although alternative perspectives continue to be part of TESOL research methodology, there are approaches to social science inquiry that are still not widely known to researchers in the field. More specifically, language education research may be argued to need further qualitative approaches that can interweave research and life, language and context, and self and society in processes of inquiry. Therefore, in this article I invite the academic community of TESOL to consider *autoethnography* as a qualitative research approach with significant potentials for research on issues of language teaching and learning. Based on a discussion of the theoretical and methodological perspectives of autoethnographic inquiry, I argue that by bringing the self and society together, such an approach can contribute to the ongoing endeavor for deepening the epistemological understanding and widening the methodological scope of research in the field.

Introduction

The quest for wider inquiry visions and more profound research approaches in language education may hardly be imagined to cease. Apart from the experimental research traditions that have continued to grow in complexity since the emergence of language teaching as an independent discipline, alternative research methodology has been among the major concerns in the field for the past three decades. Chaudron's (1986) methodological consideration of the interaction of qualitative and quantitative second language education research was among the first instances of addressing this concern. Later, the TESOL Quarterly special section on Alternatives in TESOL Research (Cumming, 1994) and the special issue of the journal on qualitative research (Davis & Lazaraton, 1995) shaped landmarks in this regard. Since then, beside the mainstream quantitative methodological discussions, other research perspectives

have continued to be debated under the rubrics of qualitative and narrative approaches (e. g. Barkhuizen, 2011; Richards, 2004), critical perspectives (e. g. Canagarajah, 1996; Davis, 2011), and, more recently, mixed-methods research (e. g. Hashemi & Babaii, 2013; Riazi, & Candlin, 2014).

Although research methodology in the field appears to be still dominated by experimental perspectives and statistical procedures (Benson, Chik, Gao, Huang, & Wang, 2009; Mirhosseini and Samar, 2015; Richards, 2009), some qualitative research traditions have already been recognized by language education researchers (e. g. Barkhuizen, Benson, & Chik, 2014; Davis, 2011, Heigham & Croker, 2009; Richards, 2004). Within the past two decades, they have demonstrated the possibility of wider research horizons and deeper wisdom in understanding issues of language teaching and learning. Narrative inquiry (Barkhuizen, 2011; Benson, 2014; Duff & Bell, 2002; Norton, 2011; Phillion & He, 2007), ethnographic research (Duff, 2013; Ramanathan & Atkinson, 1999; Watson-Gegeo, 1988), (critical) discourse analysis (Burton, 2000; Kumaravadivelu, 1999; Lin, 2014), and conversation analysis (Schegloff, Koshik, Jacoby, & Olsher, 2002; Seedhouse, 2004; Wong, 2002) are the most notable cases of such approaches. They have arguably remained *alternative* attempts far from becoming part of the mainstream trends of TESOL inquiry. But it can hardly be denied that they have enriched the field with more profound epistemological views; wider methodological perspectives; a diverse repertoire of research procedures and techniques in dealing with contextually-situated data; and greater wisdom in understanding language teaching and learning based on research findings.

However, apart from the concern that such research perspectives and practices, even in their totality, continue to remain smaller than the mainstream quantitative research trend (Benson et al., 2009; Richards, 2009), there are aspects of the social science research landscape that are still not widely known in the TESOL research community. For example, qualitative research traditions such as “phenomenology” and “grounded theory” have been stated to be “less commonly used” in the field, at least “by novice researchers” (Croker, 2009, p. 15). Introducing such less-common approaches into the realm of TESOL can probably be an important contribution as was the case for other later-introduced methods of inquiry. More specifically, I would argue that one important contribution to the field may be provided by a research approach with the capacity to help with blurring the sometimes-too-solid dichotomies of theoretician–practitioner, researcher–teacher, community–individual, and even teacher–learner. *Autoethnography* is one such hitherto less-treaded path that may lead to potentially new horizons especially in terms of bringing theory, academy, and research closer

to life, learning, and the self. In this article, I discuss the theoretical bases and methodological perspectives of autoethnographic inquiry as presented in social science qualitative research and, on this basis, I argue that the approach can be contributive to TESOL research.

Autoethnography

Autoethnographic inquiry is obviously founded on *ethnography*. The huge tradition of ethnographic research may be seen as rooted in colonialism in the nineteenth century when ethnographers were on the mission of understanding the life-world of colonized communities (Alvares, 2011). In its later academic evolution, ethnography accompanied various schools of sociological research and informed broad trends of qualitative research. Ethnographic traditions are the origin of many key elements of qualitative perspectives such as contextual situatedness, investigating the participant worldviews, and holistic exploration of *total* events. It has been claimed that qualitative sociological research has always had an autoethnographic element (Anderson, 2006) but autoethnographic approaches have increasingly shifted away from traditional ethnography to favor a more personal point of view and a more intimately understood and expressed personal voice (Ferguson, 2009). Therefore, taking ethnography as a tradition that explores social phenomena mainly on the basis of insider perspectives, with an added *auto* dimension the researcher becomes the main participant who already enjoys the insider status. “The essential difference between ethnography and autoethnography is that in an autoethnography, the researcher is not trying to become an insider in the research setting. He or she, in fact, is the insider. The context is his or her own.” (Duncan, 2004, p. 3)

The term autoethnography, apparently coined by Heider (1975), “refers to ethnographic research, writing, story, and method that connect the autobiographical and personal to the cultural, social, and political” (Given, 2008, p. 48). The central question in autoethnographic research is about how the researcher’s own lived experiences contribute to broader understandings of a sociocultural situation or a social phenomenon (Ferguson, 2009). By allowing for emotional connectivity in their research work and by writing their own selves into their research, autoethnographers challenge “accepted views about silent authorship, where the researcher’s voice is not included in the presentation of findings” (Holt, 2003, p. 2). Despite the perception of personal life as too mundane a focus for academic research, personal experiences of individuals, especially when viewed from an informed perspective of a researcher’s awareness, can create profound insights that may contribute to better understandings of broader social, cultural, and political concerns (Ellis, 1999; Pearce, 2010).

“Creating autoethnographic accounts is a way to reconcile the divide between the individual and the collective by acknowledging that individual “embodied” remembering is always “embedded” in a social context” (Pearce, 2010, p. 3). Although such an elusive concept is difficult to define as such, Spry’s (2001) account may be an extended definition of autoethnography, which she views

as a self-narrative that critiques the situatedness of self with others in social contexts... [A]utoethnographic methods recognize the reflections and refractions of multiple selves in contexts that arguably transform the authorial “I” to an existential “we.” ...Autoethnographers argue that self-reflexive critique upon one’s positionality as researcher inspires readers to reflect critically upon their own life experience, their constructions of self, and their interactions with others within sociohistorical contexts... (pp. 710–711)

By recognizing and articulating the personal voice of the researcher as a member of a social community (Johnston & Strong, 2008) and by connecting the personal experience to the social context, autoethnographic research enhances the depth of understandings created through research (Humphreys, 2005). It “enables researchers to use data from their own life stories as situated in sociocultural contexts in order to gain an understanding of society through the unique lens of self” (Chang, Ngunjiri, & Hernandez, 2013, p. 18).

Autoethnographers can, therefore, understand the meanings of their research through an active reinterpretation of their own perspectives of the issue that is being explored (Marshall & Rossman, 1999; Mykhalovskiy, 1996). In this sense, researchers can hardly reduce themselves to neutral and impartial recorders, interpreters, and reporters (Smith, 2005). Perhaps that is why autoethnography has also been seen as a critical and transformative research approach (Adams, Jones, & Ellis, 2015; Boylorn & Orbe, 2014; Custer, 2014; Neuman, 1996). A considerable aspect of such a perspective is not only for the researcher but also for the research audience to be invited to see the social concerns through the lens of their personal life events and challenges and also to view the social events as a door inwards in search of personal meaning, understanding, and learning (Ellis, 1998; Mizzi, 2010).

Like other research approaches, autoethnography may be understood in terms of branches, categories, and tendencies. One aspect of such divergence may be seen in the variation that has been introduced in terms of the emphasis on *auto* (the self), *ethno* (culture and context), or *graphy* (the research process) (Ellis & Bochner, 2000, Ngunjiri, Hernandez, & Chang, 2010). Autoethnographic studies may tend to emphasize one of these aspects depending on the nature of the issue, the context, and researcher tendencies (Denzin, 2014).

Another major categorization of the spectrum of autoethnographic approaches is seen in the distinction between *evocative* versus *analytical* autoethnography. Evocative autoethnography is a postmodern position that focuses on liberal personal voice rather than systematic accounts of the research topic. As a strongly descriptive attempt, evocative autoethnography heavily relies on narrative and expressive discourse and is critical of traditional social science research (Bochner & Ellis, 2016). Analytic or realist autoethnography, which is critical of evocative views, provides a more sophisticated and systematic framework with an acclaimed structure of five key features: complete member researcher position; analytic reflexivity; the visibility of the researcher; dialogue with informants; and theoretical analysis and expansion (Anderson, 2006; Atkinson, 2006; Ellis, 1999).

Despite this rich research perspective, some criticisms and challenges have been raised against autoethnography. Delamont (2007) perceives the entire autoethnographic endeavor as lazy and even abusive. She criticizes it on the grounds of the lack of distance with the research subject, weakness of analytic rigor, lack of socially situated data, and the unimportance of the researcher as the focus of research. Autoethnography is also questioned for being too artistic and emotional, not being scientific and rigorous enough, lacking systematicity; weakness of fieldwork, weakness of writing standards, and bias (Ellis, Adams, & Bochner, 2011; Holt, 2003; Sparkes, 2000). Although autoethnography has its own limitations (McIlveen, 2008), such outright rejections of the approach may be ascribed to positions anchored in traditional understandings of research. The critics seem to misunderstand the concern of autoethnographers with creating meaningful knowledge that can change people and the world for the better rather than with structured notions of accuracy and rigor (Ellis et al., 2011). In other words, autoethnographic inquiry “transgresses the bounds of post-positivist social science” (Watson, 2009, p. 526) and perhaps that is why it makes a powerful way of creating new meanings and understandings.

As Ellis et al. (2011) observe, in autoethnography reliability is understood in terms of the credibility of the narrator and “validity means that a work seeks verisimilitude; it evokes in readers a feeling that the experience described is lifelike, believable, and possible, a feeling that what has been represented could be true” (p. 10). Moreover, generalizability, though important to autoethnographers, is not understood in the traditional sense, but the focus shifts to readers and the extent to which they think the autoethnographic writing is meaningful to them. The autoethnographic narrative has no claim of mainstream generalizability “but it has the potential to act as a stimulus for profound understanding of a single case and, moreover, act as a stimulus to open new intellectual vistas for the reader through a uniquely personal

meaning and empathy” (McIlveen, 2008, p. 5). Although *research* might be tangled within positivistic conceptions of objectivity, reliability, validity, and generalizability in some academic settings where hard-science-based mentalities continue to rein social science inquiry, alternative perspectives such as autoethnography do create chances of shaking such mentalities and allowing for contextually meaningful understandings rooted in real-life experiences of individuals and communities.

Autoethnography in TESOL

Autoethnography has been applied in a variety of fields to explore a diversity of research topics ranging from (higher) education, cultural identity, and gender issues, to health, nursing, and even loss and grief (e. g. Chang, 2016; Cozart, 2010; Jago, 2002; Peterson, 2015; Pillay, Naicker, & Pithouse-Morgan, 2016). The vibrant research approach of autoethnography has, nevertheless, been marginally reflected in the area of language teaching and learning. The article by Canagarajah (2012) in *TESOL Quarterly* is perhaps the only high-profile piece of autoethnographic research in the field. In that article, he explores his own lived experiences in becoming an English teacher to examine the process of professionalization in TESOL. Canagarajah first provides a brief sketch of (analytic) autoethnography as his research approach in revisiting the local and global aspects of the engagements throughout his career based on his “background as a periphery professional in TESOL” (p. 262). On this basis, he then depicts an instance of a learning move from the self to the community and makes it clear that – in his own words – “this narrative is not solely about me. There are transferable implications for teacher identities for members of other professional communities, both in the center and the periphery.” (p. 262)

Apart from this article, autoethnography has had scattered presence in the field as narrowly read research articles and brief notes (e. g. Fujieda, 2008; Lopez, 2008; Park, 2014; Wijayatilake, 2012) or graduate studies (e. g. Suhr, 2014). One such rare study explores self-reflective writing of teachers and learners of English as second language in the context of a teacher education program in the United States (Lapidus, Kaveh, & Hirano, 2013). The researchers discuss autoethnographic introspection by English language learners and teachers that may help them with gaining awareness of aspects of their own language learning and teaching. The study does depict a good case of autoethnographic research, although the focus seems to be mostly on the application of autoethnography as “an excellent *teaching tool*” (p. 38) rather than a research approach. In another study, Park (2014) investigates her own

experiences of acting as a TESOL teacher educator in Korea during two years. Relying on her notes and reflections as well as some student interviews, Park reflexively explored her own learning as part of the process of gaining deeper understandings of aspects of the TESOL context of her concern.

As for graduate studies bringing autoethnography into TESOL, Suhr's (2014) inquiry is "An Autoethnographic Inquiry of an Experienced Non-Native English Speaking Teacher in an English-Dominant Country". The thesis relies on the researcher's notes about incidents of her teaching experience during a year to explore what influenced her identity as a non-native teacher of English in an English-speaking context. Another example is the autoethnographic section of Mirhosseini's (2013) doctoral research that reviews his personal background of dealing with English as a foreign language in Iran and how it reflects prevalent ideological assumptions of TESOL. Exploring various types of documents that illustrate the researcher's experiences of English language learning and teaching during 20 years, he tries to provide a personal but socially-representative image of some aspects of TESOL ideologies in that context. In terms of linking the researcher's self and the community context, Mirhosseini's autoethnographic journey is stated to be aimed at "communicating considerable messages" for the national and possibly international TESOL "community members" (p. 203).

Even this small number of studies may depict the potential of autoethnographic research perspectives and practices in tackling difficult-to-address issues of subjectivities and identities and the socio-politics of language teaching and learning in diverse settings based on in-depth understanding of *contextual localities* and, at the same time, providing informed visions of *implied globalities*. As reflected in the sketches of these studies, while the focus is on bringing the self and society together and creating more life-like research findings and understandings, practical research procedures of data collection and exploration in autoethnographic TESOL research can be based on the repertoire of methods associated with ethnography and may eclectically adopt other qualitative research procedures as well (Adams et al., 2015). Beyond technicalities, procedures, and instruments, autoethnographic research as a part of the researcher's *being* and as an attempt at connecting research with life and self with others (Ngunjiri et al., 2010), may create prospects for rich social science inquiry including TESOL processes and practices. Such in-depth inquiry may shape possibilities for diving into deeper layers of language education contexts and language learners/teachers' experiences.

Conclusion

In autoethnographic research “we seek to understand ourselves in order to provide a shared truth to others. This can only be achieved by recognising what is valuable in our responses and our experiences” (Pearce, 2010, p. 12). Therefore, with the capacity to show how the researcher is part of a larger community in terms of perceptions and practices (Ellis & Bochner, 2000), autoethnography is a potentially fruitful approach for the broad research area of TESOL. In research involvements of the field, even with the most critically-oriented and out-of-the-box type of inquiry (e. g. Davis, 2011; Pennycook, 1999), it might be argued that the researcher–researched distance is still considerable. Teachers and researchers may need to teach and research themselves (Dressman, 2006) and the research community of the field may need to learn more about how to avoid the “death of the self” (Kress, 2011, p. 35) in academic research. Through an approach to inquiry that “connects the personal to the cultural, placing the self within a social context” (Holt, 2003, p. 2), many research concerns in TESOL can be addressed and hitherto less-understood corners of language education and applied linguistics may be explored.

Specifically, one may view the argument in this article within the context of the considerable recognition of the role of identities in TESOL (e. g. Varghese, Motha, Trent, Park, & Reeves, forthcoming 2016) that has created rich discussions of issues such as non-native language teacher characteristics (e. g. Agudo, forthcoming 2017) and cultural contextualization of (English) language education (e. g. Houghton, Rivers, & Hashimoto, forthcoming 2017). With such concerns probably shaping an important part of the future agenda of the field, congruent contextually-relevant and culturally-sensitive research approaches may also be required in venturing into less-explored research realms. In the context of sometimes-forbidding academic TESOL research obsessed with positivist technicalities, autoethnography may allow for creating personally-meaningful understandings rooted in the lived experiences and the unique voice of unique individuals and communities (Pathak, 2010) that may also be more meaningfully interconnected with diversities around the world.

The Author

Seyyed-Abdolhamid Mirhosseini is an Assistant Professor at Alzahra University, Iran. His research areas include sociopolitics of language education and qualitative research methodology. His writing has appeared in journals including *Applied Linguistics*; *Language, Culture and Curriculum*; *Critical Inquiry in Language Studies*; and *Journal of Multicultural Discourses*. His most recent book is the forthcoming edited volume of *Reflections on Qualitative Research in Language and Literacy Education* (Springer, 2017).

References

- Adams, T. E., Jones, S. T., & Ellis, C. (2015). *Autoethnography*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Agudo, J. M. (forthcoming 2017). *Native and non-native teachers in second language classrooms: Professional challenges and teacher education*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Alvares, C. (2011). A critique of Eurocentric social science and the question of alternatives. In S. Ghahremani-Ghajr and S. A. Mirhosseini (Eds.), *Confronting academic knowledge* (pp. 32–57). Tehran: Iran University Press.
- Anderson, L. (2006). Analytic autoethnography. *Journal of Contemporary Ethnography*, 35(4), 373–395. DOI: 10.1177/0891241605280449
- Atkinson, P. (2006). Rescuing autoethnography. *Journal of Contemporary Ethnography*, 35(4), 400–404. DOI: 10.1177/0891241606286980
- Barkhuizen, G. (Ed.). (2011). Special issue on Narrative Research in TESOL. *TESOL Quarterly*, 45(3).
- Barkhuizen, G., Benson, P., & Chik, A. (2014). *Narrative inquiry in language teaching and learning research*. New York: Routledge.
- Benson, P. (2014). Narrative inquiry in applied linguistics research. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 34, 154–170. DOI: dx.doi.org/10.1017/S0267190514000099
- Benson, P., Chik, A., Gao, X., Huang, J., & Wang, W. (2009). Qualitative research in language teaching and learning journals, 1997–2006. *The Modern Language Journal*, 93(1), 79–90. DOI: 10.1111/j.1540-4781.2009.00829.x
- Bochner, A. & Ellis, C. (2016). *Evocative autoethnography: Writing lives and telling stories*. London: Routledge.
- Boylorn, R. M. & Orbe, M. P. (Eds.). (2014). *Critical autoethnography: Intersecting cultural identities in everyday life*. Walnut Creek, CA: Left Coast Press.
- Burton, J. (2000). Learning from discourse analysis in the ESOL classroom. *TESOL Journal*, 9(4), 24–27. DOI: 10.1002/j.1949-3533.2000.tb00279.x
- Canagarajah, A. S. (1996). From critical research practice to critical research reporting. *TESOL Quarterly*, 30(2), 321–331. DOI: 10.2307/3588146
- Canagarajah, A. S. (2012). Teacher development in a global profession: An autoethnography. *TESOL Quarterly*, 46(2), 256–279. DOI: 10.1002/tesq.18
- Chang, H. (2016). Autoethnography in health research: Growing pains? *Qualitative Health Research*, 26(4), 443–51. DOI: 10.1177/1049732315627432.

- Chang, H., Ngunjiri, F. W., & Hernandez, K. C. (2013). *Collaborative autoethnography*. Walnut Creek, CA: Left Coast Press.
- Chaudron, C. (1986). The interaction of quantitative and qualitative approaches to research: A view of the second language classroom. *TESOL Quarterly*, 20(4), 709–717. DOI: 10.2307/3586521
- Cozart, S. C. (2010). When the spirit shows up: An autoethnography of spiritual reconciliation with the academy. *Educational Studies*, 46(2), 250–269. DOI: 10.1080/00131941003614929
- Croker, R. A. (2009). An introduction to qualitative research. In J. Heigham and R. A. Croker (Eds.), *Qualitative research in applied linguistics: A practical introduction* (pp. 3–24). New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Cumming, A. (Ed.). (1994). Alternatives in TESOL research: Descriptive, interpretive, and ideological Orientations. *TESOL Quarterly*, 28(4), 673–703. DOI: 10.2307/3587555
- Custer, D. (2014). Autoethnography as a transformative research method. *The Qualitative Report*, 19(How To 21), 1-13. Retrieved from <http://www.nova.edu/ssss/QR/QR19/custer21.pdf>
- Davis, K. A. (Ed.). (2011). *Critical qualitative research in second language studies: Agency and advocacy*. Charlotte, NC: Information Age Publishing.
- Davis, K. A. & Lazaraton, A. (Eds.). (1995). Special issue on Qualitative Research in ESOL. *TESOL Quarterly*, 29(3).
- Delamont, S. (2007). Arguments against auto-ethnography. *Qualitative Researcher*, 4(1), 2–4.
- Denzin, N, K. (2014). *Interpretive autoethnography* (2nd ed.). London: Sage.
- Dressman, M. (2006). Teacher, teach thyself: Teacher research as ethnographic practice. *Ethnography*, 7(3), 329–356. DOI: 10.1177/1466138106069524
- Duff, P. (2013). *Ethnographic research in applied linguistics: Exploring language teaching, learning, and use in diverse communities*. London: Routledge.
- Duff, P. & Bell, J. S. (2002). *Narrative research in TESOL: Narrative inquiry: More than just telling Stories*. *TESOL Quarterly*, 36(2), 207–213. DOI: 10.2307/3588331
- Duncan, M. (2004). Autoethnography: Critical appreciation of an emerging art. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 3(4), 1–14, Article 3. Retrieved January 18, 2010 from http://www.ualberta.ca/~iiqm/backissues/3_4/pdf/duncan.pdf.

- Ellis, C. (1998). Exploring loss through autoethnographic inquiry: Autoethnographic stories, co-constructed narratives, and interactive interviews. In J. Harvey (Ed.), *Perspectives on loss: A sourcebook* (pp. 49–61). New York: Brunner and Mazel.
- Ellis, C. (1999). Heartful autoethnography. *Qualitative Health Research*, 9(5), 669–683.
DOI: 10.1177/104973299129122153
- Ellis, C., Adams, T. E., & Bochner, A. P. (2011). Autoethnography: An overview. *Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 12(1), Art. 10. Retrieved April 11, 2012 from <http://www.qualitative-research.net/index.php/fqs/article/view/1589/3095>
- Ellis, C., & Bochner, A. P. (2000). Autoethnography, personal narrative, reflexivity. In N. Denzin and Y. Lincoln (Eds.), *Handbook of qualitative research* (2nd ed.) (pp. 733–68). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Ferguson, A. (2009). “Healthy seeds planted in rich soil”: Phenomenological and autoethnographic explorations of ethnodrama. Unpublished Master’s Thesis, University of Saskatchewan, Canada.
- Fujieda, Y. (2008). Looking back on my personal academic literacy development in English: An autoethnographic approach of second language learning. *Kyoai Journal*, 8, 75–90. Retrieved November 3, 2014, from <http://www.kyoai.ac.jp/college/ronshuu/no-08/fujieda.pdf>
- Given, L. M. (Ed.). (2008). *The Sage encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. London: Sage.
- Hashemi, M. R., & Babaii, E. (2013). Mixed methods research: Toward new research designs in applied linguistics. *The Modern Language Journal*, 97(4), 828–852. DOI: 10.1111/j.1540-4781.2013.12049.x
- Heider, K. G. (1975). What do people do? Dani auto-ethnography. *Journal of Anthropological Research*, 31(1), 3–17. DOI: 10.1086/jar.31.1.3629504
- Heigham, J. & Croker, R. A. (Eds.). (2009). *Qualitative research in applied linguistics: A practical introduction*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Holt, N. L. (2003). Representation, legitimation, and autoethnography: An autoethnographic writing story. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 2(1), Article 2. Retrieved September 23, 2010, from, http://www.ualberta.ca/~iiqm/backissues/2_1final/html/holt.html
- Houghton, S. A., Rivers, D. J. & Hashimoto, K. (forthcoming 2017). *Beyond native-speakerism: Current explorations and future visions*. New York: Routledge.

- Humphreys, M. (2005). Getting personal: Reflexivity and autoethnographic vignettes. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 11(6), 840–860. DOI: 10.1177/1077800404269425
- Jago, B. J. (2002). Chronicling an academic depression. *Journal of Contemporary ethnography*, 31(6), 729–757. DOI: 10.1177/089124102237823
- Johnston, D. and Strong, T. (2008). Reconciling voices in writing an autoethnographic thesis. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 7(3), 47–61.
- Kress, T. M. (2011). *Critical praxis research: Breathing new life into research methods for teachers*. Dordrecht, Netherlands: Springer.
- Kumaravadivelu, B. (1999). Critical classroom discourse analysis. *TESOL Quarterly*, 33(3), 453–484. DOI: 10.2307/3587674
- Lapidus, A., Kaveh, Y. M., & Hirano, M. (2013). ESL Teachers/ESL Students: Looking at Autoethnography through the Lens of Personetics. *L2 Journal*, 5(1), 19–42.
- Lin, A. (2014). Critical discourse analysis in applied linguistics: A methodological review. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 34, 213–232. DOI: dx.doi.org/10.1017/S0267190514000087
- Lindlof, L. & Taylor B. (2002). *Qualitative communication research methods*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Lopez, L. (2008). An autoethnographic reflection of a Colombian language teacher in the making. *Essential Teacher*, 5(3), 16–18.
- Marshall, C. & Rossman, G. (1999). *Designing qualitative research* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, USA: Sage.
- McIlveen, P. (2008). Autoethnography as a method for reflexive research and practice in vocational psychology. *Australian Journal of Career Development*, 17(2), 13–20. DOI: 10.1177/103841620801700204
- Mirhosseini, S. A. (2013). Ideologies of English language teaching research in Iran: An ethnomethodological and autoethnographic inquiry. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Tarbiat Modares University, Tehran, Iran.
- Mirhosseini, S. A. & Samar. R. G. (2015). Ideologies of English language teaching in Iranian academic research: Mainstream, alternative, and beyond. *Critical Inquiry in Language Studies*, 12(2), 110–136. DOI: 10.1080/15427587.2015.1032071
- Mizzi, R. (2010). Unraveling researcher subjectivity through multivocality in autoethnography. *Journal of Research Practice*, 6(1), Article M3. Retrieved June 4, 2012, from <http://jrp.icaap.org/index.php/jrp/article/view/201/185>

- Mykhalovskiy, E. (1996). Reconsidering table talk: Critical thoughts on the relationship between sociology, autobiography and self-indulgence. *Qualitative Sociology*, 19(1), 131–151. DOI: 10.1007/BF02393251
- Neuman, M. (1996). Collecting ourselves at the end of the century. In C. Ellis and A. Bochner (Eds.), *Composing ethnography: Alternative forms of qualitative writing*. London: Alta Mira Press.
- Ngunjiri, F. W., Hernandez, K. C., & Chang, H. (2010). Living autoethnography: Connecting life and research. *Journal of Research Practice*, 6(1), Article E1. Retrieved May 12, 2013, from <http://jrp.icaap.org/index.php/jrp/article/view/241/186>
- Norton, B. (2011). Researcher identity, narrative inquiry, and language teaching research. *TESOL Quarterly*, 45(3), 415–439. DOI: 10.5054/tq.2011.261161
- Park, L. E. (2014). Shifting from reflective practices to reflexivity: An autoethnography of an L2 teacher educator. *English Teaching*, 69(1), 173–198.
- Pathak, A. A. (2010). Opening my voice, claiming my space: Theorizing the possibilities of postcolonial approaches to autoethnography. *Journal of Research Practice*, 6(1), Article M10. Retrieved June 29, 2011, from <http://jrp.icaap.org/index.php/jrp/article/view/231/191>.
- Pearce, C. (2010). The crises and freedoms of researching your own life. *Journal of Research Practice*, 6(1), Article M2. Retrieved August 29, 2011, from <http://jrp.icaap.org/index.php/jrp/article/view/219/184>.
- Pennycook, A. (Ed.). (1999). Special issue on Critical Pedagogy. *TESOL Quarterly*, 33(3).
- Peterson, A. L. (2015). A case for the use of autoethnography in nursing research. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 71(1), 226–233. DOI: 10.1111/jan.12501
- Phillion, J. & He, M. F. (2007). Narrative inquiry and ELT research. In J. Cummins and C. Davison (Eds.), *International handbook of English language teaching* (pp. 1003–1016). New York: Springer.
- Pillay, D., Naicker, I., & Pithouse-Morgan, K. (Eds.). (2016). *Academic autoethnographies: Inside teaching in higher education*. Rotterdam, Netherlands: Sense publishers.
- Ramanathan, V. & Atkinson, D. (1999). Ethnographic approaches and methods in L2 writing research: A critical guide and review. *Applied Linguistics*, 20(1), 44–70. DOI: 10.1093/applin/20.1.44
- Riazi, A. M., & Candlin, C. N. (2014). Mixed-methods research in language teaching and learning: Opportunities, issues and challenges. *Language Teaching*, 47(2), 135–173. DOI: 10.1017/S0261444813000505

- Richards, K. (2004). *Qualitative inquiry in TESOL*. New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Richards, K. (2009). Trends in qualitative research in language teaching since 2000. *Language Teaching*, 42(2), 147–180. DOI: 10.1017/S0261444808005612
- Schegloff, E. A., Koshik, I., Jacoby, S., & Olsher, D. (2002). Conversation analysis and applied linguistics. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 22, 3–31. DOI: dx.doi.org/10.1017/S0267190502000016
- Seedhouse, P. (2004). Conversation analysis, applied linguistics, and second language acquisition. *Language Learning*, 54(S1), 223–262. DOI: 10.1111/j.1467-9922.2004.00273.x
- Smith, C. (2005). Epistemological intimacy: A move to autoethnography. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 4(2), 68–76.
- Sparkes, A. C. (2000). Autoethnography and narratives of self: Reflections on criteria in action. *Sociology of Sport Journal*, 17(1), 21–41. DOI: 10.1123/ssj.17.1.21
- Spry, T. (2001). Performing autoethnography: An embodied methodological praxis. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 7(6), 706–732. DOI: 107780040100700605
- Suhr, M. (2014). Identity re-construction: An autoethnographic inquiry of an experienced non-native English speaking teacher in an English-dominant country. Unpublished Master's Thesis, Simon Fraser University, Burnaby, Canada.
- Varghese, M. M., Motha, S., Trent, J., Park, G., & Reeves, J. (forthcoming 2016). Special issue on Language teacher identity in multilingual education. *TESOL Quarterly*, 50(3).
- Watson, C. (2009). Picturing validity: Autoethnography and the representation of self? *Qualitative Inquiry*, 15(3), 526–544. DOI: 10.1177/1077800408318426
- Watson-Gegeo, K. A. (1988). Ethnography in ESL: Defining the essentials. *TESOL Quarterly*, 22(4), 575–592. DOI: 10.2307/3587257
- Wijayatilake, C. (2012). An autoethnographic exploration of my professional experiences as teacher trainer and principal at two international schools in Sri Lanka. *Language Teaching*, 45(3), 403–405. DOI: 10.1017/S0261444812000122
- Wong, J. (2002). “Applying” conversation analysis in applied linguistics: Evaluating dialogue in English as a second language textbooks. *International Review of Applied Linguistics in Language Teaching (IRAL)*, no 40, 37–60.